

FRACTURE OF FIBROUS COMPOSITES AT BEARING STRAIN IN END FACES IN COMPRESSION

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ABSTRACT

The mechanism of fracture was investigated of composite materials in compression, when the bearing strains in end faces arise and the fracture is localized near end faces. For modelling of the fracture mechanism considered the phenomenon of surface instability near the end face is used. Compressive loading is applied to this end face. For description of surface instability the three-dimensional linearized theory of deformable bodies stability is used. The comparison with experimental results was made for unidirectional fibrous materials with polymer and metal matrix.

Keywords: fracture, composites, end faces, compression, surface instability.

I. MAIN RELATIONS AND STATEMENTS

The foregoing considerations lead to following main statements of the present continual theory. 1. In the analysis of the phenomenon of bearing strains on end faces the influence of lateral surfaces of the specimen or of the structural element will be not accounted for. This statement allows to analyse the lower half-space ($x_3=0$). 2. The phenomenon of bearing strains on end faces at the initial stage will be assumed to occur as a result of surface stability loss near the loaded end face. Only surface instability will be analysed, when stresses and displacements attenuate at increasing distance from the end face. 3. The analysis of surface instability near the loaded end face will be carried out within the framework of the three-dimensional linearized theory of deformable bodies stability [1,2]. The second variant of the small practical deformations theory will be used [2] (precritical state is determined with the use of geometrically linear theory). 4. In the analysis of plastic failure (materials with metal matrix) the generalized conception of continuing loading will be used [1,2]. Consequently, we will not take account of the change of unloading zones in the process of stability loss. This statement allows to analyse in the general form the brittle and plastic failure. 5. The precritical state will be

assumed to be homogeneous in the analysis of surface instability near the loaded end face. 6. The external load at $X_3=0$ will be assumed "dead" load, and this validates the use of static method of analysis [2]. 7. Fibrous composites will be considered. With application to fibrous composites the unidirectional or orthogonally reinforced materials will be analysed under the condition that the direction of main reinforcement is perpendicular to the end face $X_3=0$. 8. In continual approximation these composites will be modelled by compressible homogeneous orthotropic body. The model will be used of elastic linear body at brittle fracture (in case of polymer matrix) and the model of elastic-plastic body at plastic failure (in case of metal matrix). The assumption will be made that the axes of symmetry of material properties (in continual approximation) coincide with axes of the chosen coordinate system. In case of the model of transversely isotropic body the planes $X_3=\text{const}$ will be assumed as isotropy planes.

Computational scheme is shown on the Figure 1.

Figure 1. Loaded end face of the specimen

Taking into account the foregoing main statements we will consider main relations. For three-dimensional precritical state main equations of the three-dimensional linearized theory of deformable bodies stability [2] with application to compressible bodies have the form

$$L_{m\alpha} u_\alpha = 0; \quad n, m, \alpha, \beta = 1, 2, 3;$$

$$L_{m\alpha} = \omega_{nm\alpha\beta} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x_n \partial x_\beta}; \quad \omega_{nm\alpha\beta} = \omega_{nm\alpha\beta}(\sigma_{11}^0, \sigma_{22}^0, \sigma_{33}^0) \quad (1)$$

Components of the asymmetric tensor of stresses of Kirchhoff are determined [2] from the expression

$$t_{nm} = \omega_{nm\alpha\beta} \frac{\partial u_\alpha}{\partial x_\beta} \quad (2)$$

For homogeneous precritical state (with application to the second variant of the small precritical deformations theory [2]) following relations hold

$$\begin{aligned} \omega_{nm\alpha\beta} = & \delta_{nm} \delta_{\alpha\beta} A_{n\beta} + (1 - \delta_{nm})(\delta_{n\alpha} \delta_{m\beta} + \\ & + \delta_{n\beta} \delta_{m\alpha}) \mu_{nm} + \delta_{n\beta} \delta_{m\alpha} \epsilon_{\beta\alpha}^0 \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

In [2] expressions are presented for determination of values of $A_{n\beta}$ and μ_{nm} for various models. In case of brittle fracture (polymer matrix) it may be assumed

$$A_{n\beta}, \mu_{nm} = \text{const}; \quad \mu_{nm} = G_{nm} \quad (4)$$

In case of plastic failure (metal matrix) it may also be assumed

$$\begin{aligned} A_{n\beta} = & A_{n\beta} (\epsilon_{11}^0, \epsilon_{22}^0, \epsilon_{33}^0); \\ \mu_{nm} = & \mu_{nm} (\epsilon_{11}^0, \epsilon_{22}^0, \epsilon_{33}^0) \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

The existence of relations Equation 5 complicates the analysis significantly. On the end face ($x_3=0$) the following boundary conditions hold

$$t_{3m} = 0 \quad \text{at } x_3 = 0, \quad m=1,2,3 \quad (6)$$

In view of the local character of the surface instability, the conditions of attenuation "at infinity" (at $x_3 \rightarrow -\infty$) should be put in the following form

$$u_m, t_{nm} \rightarrow 0 \quad \text{at } x_3 \rightarrow -\infty \quad (7)$$

The formulation of the problems is complete with foregoing relations and with taking account of symmetry properties for components $\omega_{nm\alpha\beta}$ [2]. Consequently, the problem of eigenvalues is obtained (relative to loading parameter ϵ_{33}^0) in the form Equations 1-7. Within the framework of the foregoing formulation we will consider now the computation of the theoretical strength limit corresponding to fracture at bearing strains in end faces. We will consider arbitrary form of stability loss in variables x_1 and x_2 , including local (in x_1 and x_2) forms of stability loss. It should be remarked that in [2] surface insta-

bility was considered when the load was applied along the plane boundary ($\sigma_{33}^0 = 0$) and only periodical (in x_1 and x_2) forms of stability loss were investigated. In case of arbitrary forms of stability loss the solution will be represented in the form of Fourier integrals

$$\begin{aligned}
 u_n &= \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} v_n(x_3, x_1, x_2) \{ \exp[-i(\alpha_1 x_1 + \alpha_2 x_2)] \} dx_1 dx_2; \\
 t_{nm} &= \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \tau_{nm}(x_3, x_1, x_2) \{ \exp[-i(\alpha_1 x_1 + \alpha_2 x_2)] \} dx_1 dx_2
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{8}$$

Introducing Equation 8 into Equations 1-7 we obtain the eigenvalues problem, formulated relative to functions v_n and t_{nm} Equation 8. The solution of this eigenvalues problem will not be presented here as the extent of the article is restricted, additional information may be found in [3,4]. Here only final expressions will be presented, obtained by exact solution of this eigenvalues problem. In the exact solution characteristic equations are obtained corresponding to surface instability near the loaded end face.

In the following only the case of uniaxial compression along the axis Ox_3 will be considered. In view of this the following condition should be assumed

$$\sigma_{11}^0 \equiv \sigma_{22}^0 = 0
 \tag{9}$$

We also introduce the following notations:

- $(\pi_3^-)_T$ - theoretical strength limit in compression along the axis Ox_3 , corresponding to the fracture of the whole specimen or structural element;
- $(\pi_3^-)_{T}^{SM}$ - theoretical strength limit in compression along the axis Ox_3 , corresponding to the fracture of the specimen or structural element at bearing in the end face;
- $(\pi_3^-)_{ex}$ - experimental value of the strength limit in compression along the axis Ox_3 , corresponding to the fracture of the whole specimen or structural element;
- $(\pi_3^-)_{ex}^{SM}$ - experimental value of the strength limit in compression along the axis Ox_3 , corresponding to the fracture of the specimen or structural element at bearing strain in the end face;
- $-(\sigma_{33}^0)_{cr}$ - critical value of the compressive load, corresponding to the internal [2] stability loss in the structure (for the whole specimen, corresponding to the infinite body);
- $-(\sigma_{33}^0)_{cr}^{SM}$ - critical value of the compressive load, corresponding to the local stability loss near the loaded end face.

Taking into account the foregoing notations and the second main statement of the presented theory the following equality may be written

$$(\Pi_3^-)_{\mathcal{T}}^{SM} = -(\sigma_{33}^c)_{c2}^{SM} \quad (10)$$

In analogous manner [5] we may also write

$$(\Pi_3^-)_{\mathcal{T}} = -(\sigma_{33}^o)_{c2} \quad (11)$$

Omitting all intermediate calculations, we will present only final results concerning the evaluation of the considered theoretical strength limits. We remark that for analysed composite materials, taking into account the notation Equations 2 and 3 following inequalities are valid

$$A_{33} \gg G_{13} ; A_{33} \gg \mu_{13} \quad (12)$$

with application to the brittle and plastic fracture. Taking into account Equation 12 with application to the case Equation 9, after some cumbersome transformations the following result is obtained

$$\begin{aligned} & [(\Pi_3^-)_{\mathcal{T}} - (\Pi_3^-)_{\mathcal{T}}^{SM}] [(\Pi_3^-)_{\mathcal{T}}]^{-1} \approx \\ & \approx \left(\frac{\mu_{13}}{A_{33}}\right)^2 \frac{A_{33}}{A_{11}} [1 - A_{12}^2 A_{11}^{-1} A_{33}^{-1}]^{-1} > 0 \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

For cases of brittle fracture in Equation 13 the value μ_{13} should be substituted for G_{13} . In view of inequalities Equation 12 for structural materials the following result is obtained

$$(\Pi_3^-)_{\mathcal{T}}^{SM} \lesssim (\Pi_3^-)_{\mathcal{T}} \quad (14)$$

It means that the values of theoretical strength limits $(\Pi_3^-)_{\mathcal{T}}$ and $(\Pi_3^-)_{\mathcal{T}}^{SM}$ differ insignificantly.

II. COMPARISON WITH EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

In our comparison of theoretical results with experimental results we will use the relation Equation 14, since in experimental studies quite frequently the values of $(\Pi_3^-)_{\mathcal{T}}^{SM}$ and $(\Pi_3^-)_{\mathcal{T}}$ are not distinguished. Values of theoretical strength limits

$(\Pi_3^-)_{\mathcal{T}}$ are computed in [5] for some materials. We consider unidirectional fibrous boron-reinforced plastic in case of brittle fracture at 50% content of fibers ($S_a = S_m = 0,5$). In this case following results were obtained

$$(\Pi_3^-)_{\text{experiment}} = 3,10 \text{ GPa} ; (\Pi_3^-)_{\mathcal{T}} = 2,00 - 3,00 \text{ GPa} \quad (15)$$

In Equation 15 in determination of $(\sigma_3^-)_T$, the scatter of properties of epoxy resin is taken account of.

We consider the unidirectional fibrous boron-aluminium at plastic failure in the case of 50% content of fibers ($S_a = S_m = 0,5$). Results were obtained [4,5] for annealed and non-annealed aluminium, we present the results in the Table 1.

Table 1. Results for the unidirectional fibrous boron-aluminium

Material	$(\sigma_3^-)_{ex}^{SM}, \text{MPa}$	$(\sigma_3^-)_T, \text{MPa}$
annealed	665	736
non-annealed	1282	1467

These results taking into account the inequality Equation 14 demonstrate a good agreement between theoretical and experimental results. Additional information and analysis of related problems are presented in monograph [5] .

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TEST METHODS

